

NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF A WAVE PROPAGATION PHENOMENA IN A COMPOSITE BEAMS USING A HYSTERETIC DAMAGE MODEL

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Abstract

The dynamic non-linear behaviour of damaged structures is becoming of primary importance in damage detection and health monitoring. Numerical and analytical simulations are used to predict damaged structure dynamic responses for a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenology and the identification of key parameters enabling an efficient and reliable defect characterisation.

Because of the inadequacy of classical non linear material model to reproduce the hysteretic behaviour of fatigue damaged materials, a new material model was implemented in a FE code. This new material model is based on Presaich and Mayergoyz (PM) space and it is capable of reproducing the material classical material non linearity, the hysteretic behaviour, and the memory effect typical of damaged materials.

The PM space model was tested against a classical non-linear model in a wave propagation investigation on a composite beam. Various levels of damages were introduced in different locations. The changes introduced by the damages modelled using the classical approach and the PM space were analysed in terms of the strain amplitude changes.

The results showed that the analysis of the harmonics generated by the presence of the damage zone can be used to detect fault presence, and therefore can be implemented in a new class of innovative non-destructive techniques that provide higher sensitivity in detecting and imaging incipient damage than those obtained by linear acoustic technologies.

INTRODUCTION

In order to extend the life of existing aircraft and/or reducing the costs of structural maintenance, there is the need to develop reliable nondestructive testing techniques, capable of assessing in a fast, accurate and cost effective manner, both local and global structural defects, before possible catastrophic failures occurs.

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Particular effort of the scientific community is devoted to the implementation of linear acoustic methods for structural health monitoring within a predictive maintenance program. Linear methods in acoustical nondestructive testing analyze the wave speed changes, the reflection of waves due to damage presence, and/or amplitude changes to assess the presence and location of structural anomalies. However, a new class of promising NDE techniques is being developed, based on the monitoring of material nonlinear elastic wave behaviour [1-3], showing that the monitoring of nonlinear elastic wave properties is more effective than linear acoustic methods, since they are able to show early signs of material degradation long before changes of linear acoustic properties.

The nonlinear mesoscopic elasticity [1-2] is based on the concept that the presence of damage introduces a significant change in the material nonlinear elastic wave behaviour. This behaviour is manifest in different ways when an excitation is applied to the structure under investigation. One of the common effects is that under resonance conditions, when the excitation is increased, a resonance frequency shift is observed. Another observed phenomenon is that when exciting a sample simultaneously with continuous waves of two separate frequencies, frequency-mixing spectral components are generated such as harmonics and the sum and difference of the excitation frequency waves (sidebands). These effects are hardly measurable in undamaged materials, but are clearly visible in damaged materials. The localized damaged portion of the material acts as a multiplier and nonlinear mixer of the excitation frequencies.

The monitoring of these phenomena can be an effective method to detect micro-damage in composite materials. The methods appear to be highly sensitive to the presence of structural changes, but the methodology has yet to be developed and applied to aircraft composite structures and much work is needed to demonstrate the effectiveness of the methods and the easy-of-implementation in a structural health monitoring system.

In order to support the development of such non-destructive system, a rigorous and robust modelling campaign of the structural behaviour of damaged material when excited by external loads is needed. In the light of these issues, this paper presents the work done on the development and the implementation of a material model able to describe the behaviour of microcracked composite material. The results showed that the presence of the damage generates harmonics of the excitation signal and by monitoring their presence a new fault detection system can be developed.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The elastic behavior of brittle materials such as rocks is characterized by nonlinear, discrete memory, hysteretical behavior. This material behavior is due to the presence of mesoscopic linkages between the rigid components. Materials with nonlinear mesoscopic elasticity stand in contrast to crystalline solids whose elasticity is due to contributions of atomic level forces, i.e. materials with atomic elasticity. While atomic elastic materials can be described by the traditional theory of elasticity [3]; mesoscopic elastic materials, for low strain levels, are well described by the P-M (Preisach-Mayergoyz) model of nonlinear elasticity, as developed in the mesoscopic model by McCall & Guyer [4-5]. In particular, experimental findings on healthy and microcracked material have shown that damaged atomic elastic materials behave as mesoscopic elastic materials and the level of nonlinearity is dependent on the damage/microcracked state of the material [6].

Due to the inadequacy of classical non linear material model to reproduce the behaviour of microcracked damaged materials, a new material constitutive model, based on Presaich and Mayergoyz (PM) space, capable of accurately describing the nonlinear, discrete memory, hysteretical behavior of such materials was implemented in our FE code. With this approach the macroscopic

behavior of the damaged material is constituted by the presence of a number of mesoscopic material cells (1-10 mm). The mesoscopic material cells are composed of a statistical collection of microscopic units (1-100 μm) with varying properties defining their stress-strain relation. The strain of these microscopic units is a combination of a classical non-linear state relation, and a non-classical addition due to hysteretic effects. Therefore, the macroscopic behavior of damaged composite material can be thought as composed by individual units whose stress strain curve is the sum of the classical non-linear and the hysteretical stress strain curve. The strain component of hysteretical unit can be thought as the strain of a micro-crack when subject to an external pressure that produces its closing and opening. This behavior is highlighted in Figure 1-a. The pressure-displacement of the microcrack is characterised by a rectangular loop defined by two couples of parameters: the two equilibrium lengths (l_o , l_c) and a pair of pressure (P_c , P_o) with $P_c \geq P_o$.

Figure 1: a) Behaviour of hysteretic mesoscopic elastic unity (HMEU)- b) Example of a Preisach – Mayergoz space (PM-space).

When the applied pressure increases from zero up to P_c , the equilibrium length of the hysteretic mesoscopic unit (HMEU) is l_o , but when the pressure equalizes P_c the equilibrium length changes and the new status is determined by the new equilibrium length l_c . In this new status, the equilibrium length remains l_c until the pressure is reduced to below P_o , where the equilibrium length is l_o . For convention, the stress generated by a compression load is considered positive.

The material nonlinear macroscopic behaviour can be imagined to be made up by a large number of units characterised by different couples of (P_c , P_o). The distribution of HMEU in the plane (P_c , P_o) of the macroscopic entity is localised below a 45 degree line, since P_c must be larger than P_o as displayed in Figure 1-b. The HMEU are usually represented in a stress–stress space, commonly termed “PM-space”, according to their values P_c and P_o . This representation is defined mathematically by specifying its density distribution $\mu(P_c, P_o)$. The distribution of the HMEU on the (P_c, P_o) plane can be derived using quasistatic measurements of the material strain according to specifically designed protocol loads [4–5]. Applying a certain load protocol, a change of the applied pressure ΔP occurs and, therefore, a certain number of HMEU closes or opens consistently with their characteristic pressures (P_c , P_o). Once the number of the HMEU units closed is known, the non-classical correction K_1 of the classical nonlinear elastic modulus K can be evaluated as follows:

$$\frac{1}{K_1} = -\frac{1}{L(P)} \frac{L(P+\Delta P) - L(P)}{\Delta P}; \quad P \rightarrow P + \Delta P$$

$$\frac{1}{K_1} = -\frac{1}{L(P)} \frac{L(P) - L(P-\Delta P)}{-\Delta P}; \quad P \rightarrow P - \Delta P$$
(1)

where the term $L(P)$ (eq. 1) is the length of the specimen, and P is the applied pressure.

$$L(P) = n_c(P) \cdot l_c + (N - n_c(P)) \cdot l_o$$

$$L(P + \Delta P) = n_c(P + \Delta P) \cdot l_c + (N - n_c(P + \Delta P)) \cdot l_o$$

$$L(P - \Delta P) = n_c(P - \Delta P) \cdot l_c + (N - n_c(P - \Delta P)) \cdot l_o$$
(2)

where N is the total number of HMEU, $n_c(P)$ is the number of HMEU closed when the pressure is P , and l_c and l_o are the equilibrium lengths of HMEU. Therefore, considering only the contribution of the HMEU to the material deformation, the strain generated by a stress P is given by the following expression:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{L_0 - L(P)}{L_0}$$
(3)

where L_0 is the initial length of specimen.

NONLINEAR FE CODE

The material constitutive modeled described above was implemented in our in-house FE code to simulate the presence of damage in composite materials. An explicit direct integration of the equation of motion (4) [14] was employed

$$[M]\{\ddot{d}\}_n + [D]\{\dot{d}\}_n + [K]\{d\}_n = \{R^{ext}\}_n$$
(4)

where $[M]$, $[D]$ and $[K]$ are respectively the mass, damping and stiffness matrix of the structure, $\{d\}_n$ is the displacement vector at the n^{th} time step, and $\{R^{int}\}_n$ is the external force vector at the n^{th} time step. By evaluating the first and the second derivative of $\{d\}_n$ using a central difference method and a lumped mass matrix, the motion equation (4) can be explicitly solved as:

$$\frac{1}{\Delta t^2} [M]\{d\}_{n+1} = \{R^{ext}\}_n - [K]\{d\}_n + \frac{1}{\Delta t^2} [M] \left((d)_n + \Delta t \{\dot{d}\}_{n-\frac{1}{2}} \right) - [C]\{\dot{d}\}_{n-\frac{1}{2}}$$
(5)

with

according to eq. (9) and (10). In the first step ($n-1/2$), for each element the element mid point axial strain was evaluated as the first derivative of the nodal displacements using the central difference method and the axial stress $\sigma_{n-1/2}$ was estimated as:

$$\sigma_{n-1/2} = E_{n-1} \varepsilon_n \quad (12)$$

Then, the axial stress $\sigma_{n-1/2}$ was inputted in the PM space algorithm, to estimate the new elastic modulus E_n . Finally the nodal internal forces were evaluated as the contributions of the left and right element elastic forces:

$$\begin{aligned} \left\{ R_e^{\text{int}} \right\}_{\text{left}} &= -E_n \varepsilon_n A \\ \left\{ R_e^{\text{int}} \right\}_{\text{right}} &= E_n \varepsilon_n A \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

The nonlinear investigation was carried out on an unconstrained 1m long bar, excited on the right edge with a harmonic load of 100kHz with amplitude changing from 50Pa to 256kPa. The quality factor Q was assumed to be 80. In order to understand the effect on the amplitude of the structure response of the hysteretic model (PM space), the bar was initially assumed linear and uniform (Linear & Uniform) with $E=150\text{GPa}$ and $\rho=1600\text{kg/m}^3$. Then, the bar was assumed completely damaged (Hyst. & Uniform) by using a PM space model with a uniform $\mu(P_c, P_o)$ in the pressure range between $\pm 5\text{Mpa}$ with an associated maximum strain (all the HMEU closed) of 0.001. Finally, the damaged zone was localised in a limited portion of the bar between 2cm and 7 cm from the excitation point. The severity of the damage was first considered constant (Hyst & Localised) by keeping constant the maximum strain to 0.001 and, then the damage severity was modulated by distributing the maximum strain according to a Gaussian distribution (Hyst & Loc & Grad).

RESULTS

By plotting the amplitude of the strain response of the fundamental harmonic against the excitation amplitude, the amplitude of a fully damaged (nonlinear bar) yields, as expected (smaller elastic module), larger amplitudes than any other configuration studied (Figure 2). The low limit was given by the fully undamaged elastic bar.

As expected from the theory, analysing the second and the third harmonics (Figure 3-Figure 4), the hysteretic nonlinearity effects can be observed more clearly than in Figure 2, since very large strain amplitudes are present in the case of material hysteretic behaviour. These results show that the presence of a cracked zone area can be detected by monitoring of the presence of the harmonics of the excited signal.

Finally, by plotting the strain amplitude of the first, of the third and of the fifth harmonics (Figure 5-Figure 7), the presence of a hysteretic nonlinearity area was detected by the presence of a reflection wave at the stiffness discontinuity zone (Hyst and Localised). A similar behaviour can be found in materials with macroscopic cracks. While the behaviour of the Hyst & Loc & Grad curves resembles the behaviour of plasticized materials in absence of macroscopic cracks.

Figure 2 - 1st Harmonic strain amplitude versus load magnitude.

Figure 3 - 2nd Harmonic strain amplitude versus strain magnitude of the 1st Harmonic

Figure 4 - 3rd Harmonic strain amplitude versus strain magnitude of the 1st Harmonic

Figure 5 - Fundamental strain amplitude versus distance ($A=256000 \text{ Pa}$).

Figure 6 - 3^{rd} Harmonic strain amplitude versus distance ($A=256000 \text{ Pa}$)

Figure 7 - 5th Harmonic strain amplitude versus distance ($A=256000$ Pa)

CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents results relative to the implementation of a new material model in a FE code, in order to describe the behaviour of damaged composite materials. In particular, this new material model, based on Presaich and Mayergoz (PM) space, is capable of reproducing the material classical material non linearity, the hysteretic behaviour, and the memory effect typical of damaged composite materials. This representation is commonly termed ‘PM-space’.

The PM space model was tested against a classical non-linear model in a wave propagation investigation on a composite beam. Various levels of damages were introduced. The results show that the damage introduces harmonics of the excitation frequencies, and wave propagation changes were analysed in terms of the harmonics amplitude differences. The monitoring of the generation of these harmonics can be used to detect fault presence, and therefore can be implemented in a new class of innovative non-destructive techniques that potentially can provide higher sensitivity in detecting and imaging incipient damage than those obtained by linear acoustic technologies.

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